

A Step Towards Equality? An Analysis of the Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2019

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ABSTRACT

The recognition and protection of the rights of persons with disabilities (PWDs) constitute an essential aspect of human rights law and social justice. In Nigeria, the legal framework governing disability rights has evolved significantly, culminating in the enactment of the Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2019. This Act's provisions aligns with international human rights instruments, particularly the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), which Nigeria ratified in 2007. However, it appears the Act has no strong will to herald the desired change envisioned therein since discriminations against PWDs are still prevalent. This research has examined the provisions of the Act to see if it is effective in doing what it was promulgated to. The aim here was to consider how the law is employed to better the lives of PWDs in areas including but not limited to access to justice, employment, healthcare, education, and transportation. It is also examined how the Act legal is adopted for the protection and integration of PWDs in Nigerian. The research found that despite the extant laws, PWDs in the Nigeria still suffer stigmatisation, denial of certain rights like right to employment; educational rights, etc. and do not enjoy significant and substantial integration into society. Based on the above, it is recommended that there should be a reform in the law especially on the implementation of the extant law *on Disability inclusion, creation of social and economic fora, social and political education, awareness programs for PWDs.*

KEYWORDS: Disability Rights, Nigerian Legal Framework, Inclusion, Human Rights Law, Disability Act, Legal Evolution, CRPD, Accessibility, Social Justice.

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1.0. INTRODUCTION

According to Inclusive Friend Association (IFA)¹ Nigeria has about 31 million persons (representing 15%) of the total population possessing one form of disability. This means, there are 15% of Nigeria's population who suffer one form of disability or the other.² Several credible studies indicate that persons with disabilities (PWDs) in Nigeria are largely excluded from, and lack access to basic services including health, education, rehabilitation, employment, economic empowerment, etc.³ In line with global trends, up to 90% of PWDs in Nigeria live in abject poverty.⁴ Although there are disability rights laws and policies at federal level and in some states, with disability agencies set up across these jurisdictions, there are still significant inclusivity and accessibility gaps, which ought to have been filled to improve the quality of lives of PWDs.

¹ Inclusive Friend Association (IFA), Situational analysis on the inclusion of persons with disabilities in social protection in Nigeria. (Aug 2021) available at <<https://asksource.info/fr/resources/situational-analysis-inclusion-persons-disabilities-social-protection-nigeria>>. Accessed 2nd March, 2025

² Waliat Musa, 31 million PLWDs suffer as 23 states neglect disability rights. Dec 3, 2021. Available at <<https://guardian.ng/news/31-million-plwds-suffer-as-23-states-neglect-disability-rights/>>. Accessed 2nd March, 2025

³ *Ibid*

⁴ (n 1)

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The report also shows that disability prevalence in Nigeria ranges between 3% - 15% of the total population but using the WHO and World Bank 2011 statistics, persons with disability in Nigeria are about 30 million. It also found that besides 90% of this population living in abject poverty, the literacy rate for youth with disabilities is 30% compared to 65% of youths without disabilities and 63% of adults with disabilities are unemployed while a huge number accounting for 30% of out of school children are those with disabilities.⁵

Evidently, while marking the 2021 International Day for Persons with Disability, one of the PWDs decried the situation of things even after the law on the protection of discrimination for the communities has been passed. He noted that;

we are concerned that 34 months after the passage of the Discrimination against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act 2018, citizens with disabilities are still left behind due to no implementation of the Act by Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs). This is evidenced by the non-provision of necessary measures to enhance access to buildings of these MDAs, and the inclusion of citizens with disabilities in their programs and activities.⁶

The above amongst other challenges makes it necessary to interrogate the effectiveness of the existing legal framework for the protection of the rights of persons with disabilities in Nigeria.

2.0. UNDERSTANDING DISABILITY

The Discrimination against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2019 defined Disability to include;

long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairment which in the interaction with various barriers may hinder full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others" and discrimination to be "differential treatment and its verbs and infinite form, discriminate, to discriminate have the corresponding signification.⁷

From the definition provided above, it is clear that the concept of disability at least suggests some condition that limits a person's performance of some activities that society expects of everybody. The condition may be the effects on the organs, body parts, or a person's participation in areas of life.

Classification of Disability

The World Health Organisation (WHO) classified Disability under the following subheadings; Body Functions, Structures and impairments, Activities and Participation /activity limitations, and participation restrictions. It also recognized that this might be affected by some contextual factors.⁸ The Organization explained these classifications by defining them thus;

a. Body Function, Structures, and Impairments: "Body Functions" are the biological functions of body systems, including mental functions. "Body structures" are functional parts such as organs, limbs, and components. At the same time, "Impairments" are problems in body function or structure, such as a significant deviation or loss.⁹

b. Activities and Participation /activity limitations and participation restrictions: This would be explained in these regards-"Activity" is the execution of a task or action by an individual.

c. "Participation" is involved in a life situation. It further stated that Activity limitations are difficulties an individual may have in executing activities, while Participation restrictions are problems an individual may experience when involved in life situations.¹⁰

WHO's classification of disability is the standardised categorisation and these authors adopts same in this research.

3.0. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A theoretical framework is a blueprint, guide, map, or plan for a research activity that describes the concepts, models, or specific theories, providing the theoretical underpinning for the research study. It is, however, essential to note that the ability of theories to fulfill this obligation depends on their suitability to explain the subject matter in question.¹¹ Given the above reality, this study will find the following theories convenient and most appropriate in assessing the accessibility of physical structures in Nigeria by disabled persons.

⁵ Inclusive Friend Association (IFA), Situational analysis on the inclusion of persons with disabilities in social protection in Nigeria. (Aug 2021) available at <<https://asksource.info/fr/resources/situational-analysis-inclusion-persons-disabilities-social-protection-nigeria>>. Accessed 2nd March, 2025

⁶ *Ibid*

⁷ Section 57 of the Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2019

⁸ Article 4 of the Introduction of the International Classification of Functioning Disabilities and Health, WHO 2001. *Ibid.* pg. 10

⁹ Article 4.1 *Ibid.* Pg. 12-13

¹⁰ Article 4.2 of the Introduction of the International Classification of Functioning Disabilities and Health, WHO 2001. Pg. 14-16

¹¹ Amali S, & Ilim M., Civil Society Organisations and Democratic Consolidation in Nigeria, (2016) available from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343493722> accessed 10th March, 2025

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3.1. The Human Rights Model of Disability

The human rights model focuses on the inherent dignity of the human being and subsequently, but only if necessary, on the person's medical characteristics. It places the individual center stage in all decisions affecting him/her and, most importantly, locates the main 'problem' outside the person and in society.¹²

Quinn et al. argued that:

In essence, the human rights perspective on Disability means viewing people with disabilities as subjects, not objects. It entails moving away from viewing people with disabilities as problems towards viewing them as rights holders. Importantly, it means locating problems outside the disabled person and addressing how various economic and social processes accommodate the difference of Disability – or not, as the case may be.¹³

This model is the inspiration for the document the UN Charter on the Rights of Disabled Persons. The law is essential because it:

i. "People with disability developed it to achieve a greater level of equality for people with disability around the World"

"Explains the steps that governments around the World must take to uphold, promote and protect the rights of people with disability".¹⁴

3.2. The Anti-Discriminatory Law Theory

The jurisprudence associated with anti-discriminatory law theory is that the purpose of enacting laws is to prohibit discrimination on the grounds of disability. Only with this purpose in mind can we fully appreciate the requirements of their legal construction.¹⁵ Moreover, failure to keep sight of this purpose in implementing such laws can result in the marginalization of the very people they are designed to protect. The call to enact non-discrimination laws about disability arose from recognizing that disability policy is as much an issue of civil rights as welfare and rehabilitation.¹⁶ This theory is the basis for enacting disability rights and protection laws. It is logical to conclude that the Discrimination against Persons with Disability (Prohibition) Act, 2019, is promulgated based on this theory.

3.3. The Social Model of Disability

This model is of the view that people are disabled because social barriers, such as buildings not having a ramp or accessible toilets, or people's attitudes, like assuming people with disabilities cannot do certain things are prevalent and are held sway by the society.¹⁷ The social model, in other words, helps us recognize barriers that make life harder for people with disabilities. Removing these barriers creates equality and offers people with disability more independence, choice, and control.¹⁸

The social model of disability is of the view that a disabled person who cannot access a building because of the stairs and wants to get into a building with a step at the entrance is not the one that has the challenge; instead, it is the building's problem and would suggest adding a ramp to the entrance.

As noted in the words of Professor Mike Oliver, a UK Professor and a Disability Rights Activist, "*The problem is not that I cannot get into a lecture theatre, the problem is that the lecture theatre is not accessible to me...*"¹⁹

Rationale for Prohibition of Discrimination against PWD

The subject matter of disability is as much a right problem as it is a welfare and rehabilitation problem. This is accomplished primarily through the disability rights movement which addresses the various societal challenges affecting the community of PWDs. This has increasingly led to the development of the social model of disability which recognises the interaction between an

¹² G. Quinn and T. Degener, 'The Moral Authority for Change: Human Rights Values and the World Wide Process of Disability Reform,' in *Human Rights and Disability: The Current Use and Future Potential of Human Rights Instruments in the Context of Disability*, eds. G. Quinn and T. Degener (United Nations, 2002), 13, 14. Available from <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-international-and-comparative-social-policy/article/human-rights-approach-to-disability-assessment/38A82E7D5EA9E662A9A61B7D8F6088F8> accessed 10th March, 2025

¹³ *Ibid*

¹⁴ Articles 6 & 9 of CRPD

¹⁵ WHITTLE, R. (2001). The concept of disability discrimination and its legal construction. In: 'Discrimination and affirmative action on the labor market - legal perspectives' (in preparation of the Swedish Presidency of the European Union), National Institute for Working Life, Sweden, 6-7 November 2001. Available from <http://shura.shu.ac.uk/information.html> accessed 10th March, 2025

¹⁶ *Ibid*

¹⁷ Guccione, Andrew A., and Cathy S. Elrod. "Health and function: patient management principles." *Geriatric Physical Therapy-eBook* (2011): 87.

¹⁸ *Ibid*

¹⁹ Australian Federation of Disability Organizations, Social Model of Disability, available from <https://www.afdo.org.au/social-model-of-disability/#:~:text=The%20social%20model%20of%20disability%20says%20that%20people%20are%20disabled,can't%20do%20certain%20things>. Accessed 10th March, 2025

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individual's impairment and his physical, environmental, and social surroundings. It consequently shows how society continues to force and foist physical and attitudinal obstacles which prevent the full participation of PWDs in everyday life. Hence, the need to come to the realisation that an individual's deficiency may not necessarily be a physical obstacle or hurdle to his participation in everyday life and society and the provisioning of a fairer platform to integrate and incorporate them into society is a legal obligation.²⁰

4.0. EXAMINATION OF DISCRIMINATION AGAINST PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES (PROHIBITION) ACT

The Discrimination against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, in its 58 sections and schedule,²¹ provides for the full integration of PWDs in Nigeria by making laudable provisions on the rights and privileges of persons with disabilities. This section of the research provides an overview of the Act.

It is essential to know that while the Act provides a five years transitory period (from its enactment) to enable modification of public structures/services to meet the peculiar needs of persons with disabilities, other provisions are, in fact, to be implemented almost immediately by the import of the requirements of the Act.

Accordingly, the Act is arranged into the following sections; the first part makes provision for the Prohibition of Discrimination and Awareness Programs which is contained in sections 1-2, the second part handles issues pertaining to the Accessibility of Physical Structures by persons with disabilities and is provided in sections 3-8, the third part makes provision for Road Transportation, in the fourth part, the Act make provisions for Seaports, Railways, and Airport Facilities under sections 13-15, the fifth part of the Act provide for the rights of PWDs which include; right to liberty, rights to education, health, and first consideration in queues, accommodation, and in emergencies. The Act makes provisions for opportunity for employment and participation in politics and public life of PWDs. Part seven of the Act established the National Commission for Persons with Disabilities (NCPWD) while the provisions for the appointment and duties of the Executive Secretary and other staff of the Commission is provided under the eight part. The ninth part is dedicated to miscellaneous provisions while the tenth and the last part of the Act is the interpretation section. The Act altogether has a total of ten parts and a schedule. Below is the overview of each part of the Act.

PART I- PROHIBITION OF DISCRIMINATION AND AWARENESS PROGRAMS (SECTIONS 1-2)

a. Prohibition of Discrimination and Awareness Programs

The Act prohibits the discrimination of a person on the ground of his/her disability.²² Accordingly, a corporate body that discriminates on this ground is subject to a fine of N1,000,000, while an individual is liable to pay an N100,000 fine, face a six months imprisonment term or both.²³

To enforce the above, the Act provides that the person may also bring a civil action against discriminated against as the Act outlaws discrimination in its totality and under any manner or circumstance.²⁴

b. Awareness Programs

The Act places the responsibility of promoting the rights and dignity of persons with disabilities and their contributions with the Federal Ministry of Information.²⁵

PART II- ACCESSIBILITY OF PHYSICAL STRUCTURE (SECTIONS 3-8)

c. Right of access to public Structures

The Act guarantees a person with disability a right to access the physical environment and buildings on an equal basis with others.²⁶ This provision is further complemented by sections 4 and 5 of the Act, which requires public facilities to be accessible and usable by persons with disabilities. The public facilities include road sidewalks, pedestrian crossings, special facilities such as elevators, crutches, guide canes, toilet facilities, and door protective and re-opening devices. The facilities are to reflect inclusivity in access to public structures by all, abled or disabled.

d. Transitory Period

The Act gives a five years transitory period from its inception, within which all public buildings or structures, whether immovable or not, must be modified and accessible to persons with disabilities, including those in wheelchairs.²⁷

e. Building Plan

²⁰ S 42 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as altered)

²¹ PLAC, Arrangement of Sections. Available from <https://placng.org/i/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/The-Discrimination-Against-Persons-with-Disabilities-Prohibition-Act.pdf>. Accessed 9th March, 2025

²² S. 1(1) of the DAPDA, 2019

²³ Ibid at s. 1(2)

²⁴ Ibid at s.1(3)

²⁵ Ibid at S. 2

²⁶ Ibid at s. 3

²⁷ Ibid at s. 6

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The Act provides the procedure for erecting public structures, so it conforms to a building code that has accessibility features for persons with disabilities, including those in the wheelchair²⁸. Section 7(2) prohibits government bodies, agencies, or individuals responsible for approving building plans from approving plans that fail to provide such accessibility features. Officers who do this are liable on conviction to a fine of at least N1, 000,000 (One Million Naira), an imprisonment term of two years, or both. Persons with disabilities may also seek to redress this right in court by notifying the relevant authority of the existence of the state of inaccessibility.²⁹ On notification, the relevant authority is expected to take the necessary steps to remove the barrier and make the environment accessible.

Interestingly, corporate bodies who fail to comply with such notice may face a fine of N10, 000 in damages for every day of default. This position is slightly different for contravening individuals who face N5, 000 in damages for each day of default, a six months imprisonment term, or both.³⁰

PART III – ROAD TRANSPORTATION (SECTIONS 9-12)

f. Goods, services, and Facilities

The Act prevents a person who provides goods and services from discriminating against a person with a disability either in the terms and conditions for providing the said goods and services or by refusing to avail its facilities to him/her.³¹

g. Accessibility of vehicles

The Act mandates government providers to make provisions for lifts, ramps, and other accessibility aids that enhance the accessibility of their vehicles, parks, and bus stops to persons with disabilities.³²

It also mandates every public vehicle to have a functional audible and visual display of its destination within five years of the commencement of this Act.³³ A similar provision to section 10(1) is provided in section 11 for all transport service providers. Section 11 also mandates the regular and frequent maintenance of accessibility aids and equipment in vehicles.

In addition, section 11(4) places a duty of care on a driver who must ensure that his vehicle stops before a person with Disability alights from the vehicle. There is also a responsibility placed on all intending passengers to wait for a person with a Disability to board before them.³⁴

h. Reserved Places

The Act provides for suitable places to be marked and reserved for persons with disabilities. However, to be entitled to a reserved parking space, it is expected that the car can be identified with the necessary insignia (sign, symbol, etc.)³⁵

A person/organization/ corporate body in control of a public parking lot who fails to provide reserved parking spaces for persons with disabilities is liable to pay N1,000 for each day of default.³⁶

A person without disability commits an offense if he/she also parks in a reserved space and could pay a fine of N5, 000 on conviction. Additionally, a person who intentionally obstructs the reserved space is liable to a fine of N5, 000 if convicted.³⁷

PART IV -SEAPORTS, RAILWAYS, AND AIRPORT FACILITIES (SECTIONS 13-15)

i. Seaports and Railway and Airport

This mandates airlines operating in Nigeria to ensure that their facilities are accessible to persons with Disability.³⁸ For instance, making available presentable and functional wheelchairs, ensuring that persons with disabilities are assisted to go on and off-board in safety and comfort and according priority to persons with disabilities in boarding and disembarking from the aircraft.³⁹

Section 13 of the Act also mandates seaport facilities, vessels, railway stations, and trains to be accessible to persons with disabilities. However, unlike airline operations, there is a proviso of five years to modify their operations. The also provides for airports to make available functional assistive and protective devices to and from the airport.⁴⁰

There is a provision for all general information to be translated into an accessible format appropriate to the person with a disability present.⁴¹

²⁸ Ibid at s. 7

²⁹ Ibid at s. 8

³⁰ Ibid at s. 8(2)

³¹ Ibid at s. 9

³² Ibid at s. 10(1)

³³ Ibid at s. 10(2)

³⁴ Ibid at s. 11(5).

³⁵ Ibid at s. 12(2)

³⁶ Ibid at s. 12(3)

³⁷ Ibid at s. 12(4)

³⁸ Ibid at 14 (1(a)

³⁹ section 14(b)-(d)

⁴⁰ section 14(2)

⁴¹ section 15

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PART V – LIBERTY, RIGHTS TO EDUCATION, HEALTH, AND FIRST CONSIDERATION IN QUEUES, ACCOMMODATION, AND IN EMERGENCIES (SECTIONS 16-27)

j. Prohibition of use of Persons with Disability in soliciting for alms and penalty

The Act provides that a person shall not employ, use or involve a person with a disability in begging or parading them in public with the intention of soliciting for alms⁴². Persons who violate this are liable on conviction to a fine of N100, 000, a term of 6 months imprisonment or both⁴³

k. Right to Free Education

The Act entitles a person with disability to a right to education free from discrimination. It also allows a person with a disability free education up to the secondary level and mandates the NCPWD to provide educational assistive devices.

The provision in section 17 is further complemented by section 18, which mandates all public schools from primary to tertiary to be inclusive of and accessible to persons with disabilities.

To achieve this, the Act mandates the provision of special facilities and at least one trained personnel to cater to the education of persons with disabilities in every school⁴⁴. It also mandates the inclusion of braille, sign language, and other skills to form part of the curricula in primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions.⁴⁵

l. Subsidized education for special education personnel

The Act provides for subsidized education for special education personnel.⁴⁶ The provision complements sections 17 and 18, providing the right to free education and inclusiveness.

m. Appropriate Mode of Education for Persons with Disabilities

This includes the education of persons with disabilities (especially children) to be communicated in the most appropriate language and mode, irrespective of whether they are blind, deaf, or with multiple disabilities.⁴⁷

n. Free Healthcare

The Act mandates the government to provide persons with disabilities free access to adequate healthcare without discrimination. It also entitles persons with mental Disabilities to free medical and health services in all public institutions.⁴⁸

o. Certificate of Disability

The Act provides that a Person with disability must obtain a permanent certificate of disability (PCD) from the NCPWD.⁴⁹ However, a temporary certificate of disability may be issued by a doctor with approval of the Commission if the doctor suspects disability in the course of treatment of a person who was not a person of disability before.⁵⁰ Where this disability, however, persists for over 180 days, the Commission, on the recommendation of the doctor, shall issue a permanent state of disability.⁵¹

Persons who unlawfully issue or obtain a certificate of disability are liable on conviction to a fine of N200, 000, an imprisonment term of one year or both.⁵²

Public hospitals are also mandated to provide special communication where a person with communicational disabilities is medically attended to.⁵³

p. The situation of Risk and Humanitarian Emergencies

The Act provides for the safety and protection of persons with disabilities in disasters, emergencies, risks, or violence by the government with due regard to their peculiar vulnerabilities.⁵⁴ Persons with disabilities are also expected to be accorded priority in queues and consideration when free accommodation is provided by schools, service providers, government, and organizations.⁵⁵

⁴² *Ibid at s.16(1)*

⁴³ section 16(2)

⁴⁴ S. 18 of the Act

⁴⁵ *Ibid*

⁴⁶ S. 19 of the Act

⁴⁷ S. 20 of the Act

⁴⁸ S. 21

⁴⁹ *Ibid at s. 22(1)*

⁵⁰ S. 22(2)

⁵¹ S. 22(3)

⁵² *Ibid at s. 23*

⁵³ *Ibid at s. 24*

⁵⁴ S. 25

⁵⁵ Ss 26 &27

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PART VI- OPPORTUNITY FOR EMPLOYMENT AND PARTICIPATION IN POLITICS AND PUBLIC LIFE (SECTIONS 28-30)

q. Equal Right to Work

This guarantees a person with disability the right to work and earn a living in a labor market/work environment free from limitations.⁵⁶ Persons and companies who breach this provision are liable on conviction to nominal damages of a minimum of N250, 000 payable to the affected person (when an individual commits the offense) or N500, 000 (when a company commits the offense). A company's principal officers are also liable to pay N50, 000 damages to the affected person with disability under this provision.⁵⁷ The Act equally provides that Employers of labor in public institutions shall have at least 5% of persons with disabilities in their employment.⁵⁸

r. Participation in politics

The Act under this provision encourages persons with disabilities to participate fully in politics and public life. It also mandates the government to promote an environment where persons with disabilities can engage in public affairs in non-governmental organizations, associations, and in the administration of political parties.⁵⁹

PART VII- ESTABLISHMENT OF THE NATIONAL COMMISSION FOR PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES (SECTIONS 31-39)

s. Establishment of the National Commission for Persons with Disabilities

This establishes a NCPWD under the Presidency. The head office of the Commission shall be in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT)⁶⁰

t. Establishment and Membership of Governing Council

This establishes a Governing Council consisting of a part-time chairman and eighteen (18) other members who are responsible for steering the affairs of the Commission.⁶¹ The eighteen members are drawn from persons with disabilities from each of the six geopolitical zones, a representative from the Federal Ministries of Education, Health, Sports, Women Affairs, Housing, Transport, Environment, Labour and Productivity, Justice, Finance, the National Human Rights Commission and the National Planning Commission.⁶² The Chairman of the Council and the representative from each of the six geopolitical zones shall be appointed by the President subject to confirmation of the Senate.⁶³

The Chairman and Members of the Council shall hold office for a renewable term of four years or on such terms and conditions as may be specified in their letter of appointment.⁶⁴ However, they will cease to hold office as a Member of the Council for various grounds such as becoming bankrupt, being guilty of gross misconduct in relation to his duty, or resigning his/her appointment.⁶⁵ The President may also remove him/her on recommendation by the Council if it is not in the interest of the Commission or the public that he/she continues to remain.⁶⁶ However, where this happens, another person representing the same interest must be appointed by the Council if an unexpired term remains.⁶⁷

u. Powers of the Council

Powers of the Governing Council include managing the affairs of the Commission, employing a staff of the Commission with such remuneration, and entering into contracts to discharge its duties. The Council is also responsible for receiving, disbursing, and accounting for funds of the Commission.⁶⁸

v. Functions of the Commission

The Act outlines the functions of the Commission. They include making available not less than 5% of the workforce to persons with disabilities, collecting data and records on the special education of persons with disabilities, facilitating the procurement of scholarships awards for persons with disabilities up to the university level, ensuring that facilities are built in every community to accommodate the special needs of persons with disabilities, promoting and uplifting the social well-being of persons with disabilities by encouraging the public to change their attitude towards them, procuring assistive devices for all disability types, receiving

⁵⁶ S. 27(1)

⁵⁷ section 28(2) and (3)

⁵⁸ Ibid s. 29

⁵⁹ S. 30 of the Act

⁶⁰ S. 31 of the Act

⁶¹ section 32(2)

⁶² Section 32(2)

⁶³ section 32(3)

⁶⁴ , section 34

⁶⁵ section 35(1)

⁶⁶ in section 35(3)

⁶⁷ in section 35(2)

⁶⁸ S. 37

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complaints by persons with disabilities on violation of their rights and issuing the insignia of identification for persons with disabilities among others.⁶⁹

PART VIII- APPOINTMENT AND DUTIES OF THE EXECUTIVE SECRETARY AND OTHER STAFF (SECTIONS 40-51)

w. Powers of the Commission, Appointment, and duties of the Executive Secretary of the Commission

The Act gives NCPWD the power to do any lawful thing that can facilitate carrying out any of its functions. These include entering into contracts for the education of persons with disabilities, selling, leasing, or disposing of any property, acquiring assets necessary for the conduct of its business, and sponsoring research for the performance of its functions, among others.

The Commission may also acquire any land for the purpose of performing any of its functions.⁷⁰ S. 40 of the Act provides for an Executive Secretary of the Commission who shall be responsible for the execution of its policies and daily administration. Apart from having the requisite qualification and experience appropriate to perform the office functions, the Executive Director must be a person with Disability.

x. Funds of the Commission and Annual Estimate Expenditure

This establishes a Fund for the Commission to settle all expenses incurred by it. This includes its cost of administration, payment of salaries, remuneration, and anything done in relation to its functions.⁷¹

Budgetary allocations from the Federal Government or monies granted by anybody or institution within or outside Nigeria shall be credited to the Fund.⁷²

In addition, the Commission may also accept a gift of land, money, or property on terms and conditions that are not inconsistent with any law.⁷³ It may also borrow to execute or complete some special projects⁷⁴. It should be noted Court judgments made against the Commission shall be paid from the Fund of the Commission.⁷⁵ This provides for keeping the accounts and records of transactions by the Commission, which must ensure all payments from the Fund are authorised.⁷⁶

The Auditor General for the Federation is responsible for inspecting and auditing the records of the Commission and drawing the attention of the Secretary to the Government of the Federation to any irregularities disclosed by his/her inspection and audit.⁷⁷

The Commission must also submit an annual review of its activities to the Secretary to the Government of the Federation by 30th June every year, while a copy of its audited accounts and annual report must be submitted to the National Assembly.⁷⁸ The Governing Council must ensure that the Commission's accounts are audited quarterly and externally once a year.⁷⁹

PART IX- MISCELLANEOUS PROVISIONS, INTERPRETATION, AND SCHEDULE– (SECTIONS 52-58)

y. Indemnity of Officers

This provision indemnifies a Member of the Council, Executive Secretary, officer, or employee of the Commission from civil or criminal proceedings.

A notice, summons, or document required to be served on the Commission may be served by delivering it to the Executive Secretary or by sending it through registered post addressed to the Executive Secretary at the head office in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT).⁸⁰ The Act provides the ground on which one can be entitled to damages when his rights are violated. Accordingly, the victim or claimant of the said damages is to prove the violation of the said provisions and not necessarily specific damages.

z. Power of regulation and Interpretation

The Council, under the law, has the power to make regulations for the implementation of the provisions of the Act.⁸¹ Key terms used in the Act, such as discrimination, persons with disabilities, public buildings, etc., are defined under s. 57 of the Act.

⁶⁹ S. 38 of the Act

⁷⁰ S. 51 of the Act

⁷¹ S. 45(2)

⁷² S. 45(1)

⁷³ S. 46

⁷⁴ S. 47

⁷⁵ S. 53

⁷⁶ S. 48

⁷⁷ S. 49

⁷⁸ S. 50

⁷⁹ S. 45(3)

⁸⁰ S. 52

⁸¹ S. 56 of the Act

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5.0. RIGHTS OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES UNDER THE DISCRIMINATION AGAINST PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES (PROHIBITION) ACT, 2019

Persons with disabilities are no fewer humans, as such, are entitled to the same rights and privileges that every member of a society is entitled to. They are to be accorded some special rights based on their circumstances. As noted by the Council of Europe, people with disabilities have the Right to access all aspects of society equally, including the physical environment, transportation, information and communications, and other facilities and services provided to the public.⁸²

Furthermore, it is imperative to note that the prohibition of discrimination against disabled persons is a constitutional right guaranteed under section 42 (2) of the 1999 constitution.

Under the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, they have rights ranging from equality and non-discrimination,⁸³ exceptional care for women and children with disabilities,⁸⁴ Right of access to physical structures and justice,⁸⁵ freedom from torture or cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, exploitation, violence, and abuse, etc.⁸⁶

Accordingly, the Act guarantee the following rights;

a. **Educational Rights:** The act guarantees free education up to secondary school for persons with disabilities.⁸⁷ The schools are to cater for the physically challenged people's needs.⁸⁸ It requires all public schools to have trained personnel or special facilities for their education, including braille and sign language.⁸⁹

b. **Healthcare Rights:** Individuals with disabilities have the right to accessible healthcare without discrimination.⁹⁰

c. **Accessibility Rights:** The act mandates accessibility to physical structures,⁹¹ including public buildings, roads, sidewalks, and transportation.⁹² It also prohibits approval of building plans without disability accommodations.⁹³

d. **Employment Rights:** PWDs have the right to work on an equal basis with others and gain employment in a labor market.⁹⁴

e. **Right to first consideration in queues,⁹⁵ in given accommodation,⁹⁶ healthcare situations, and Emergencies:** Persons with disabilities are given priority in queues, accommodation, healthcare situations, and emergencies.⁹⁷ Safety measures should consider their vulnerability.⁹⁸

f. **Prohibition of Discrimination:** The act prevents isolation, discrimination, segregation, or compulsory confinement of persons with disabilities.⁹⁹

g. **Prohibition of Exploitation:** The act condemns the use of disabled individuals for soliciting alms by exploiting their disabilities.¹⁰⁰

h. **Right to Participate in Politics and Public Life:** The act promotes the political participation of individuals with disabilities and encourages the development of related policies¹⁰¹.

⁸² Council of Europe, Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, <https://www.coe.int/en/web/compass/convention-on-the-rights-of-persons-with-disabilities#> accessed 26th January 2025

⁸³ Art 5 of the CRPD

⁸⁴ *Ibid* at art 6&7

⁸⁵ *Ibid* at art 9 &13

⁸⁶ *Ibid* at art 15&16

⁸⁷ S. 17 of the Disability Act

⁸⁸ *Ibid* at ss. 18, 19 & 20

⁸⁹ *Ibid*

⁹⁰ S. 21 of DAPDDA

⁹¹ *Ibid* at ss. 3&4

⁹² Part iii & iv of the Act

⁹³ S. 7(2)

⁹⁴ *Ibid* at ss. 6 & 28

⁹⁵ *Ibid* at s. 26(1)

⁹⁶ *Ibid* at s.27

⁹⁷ S. 24

⁹⁸ S. 25

⁹⁹ S.1 of the Act

¹⁰⁰ S. 16

¹⁰¹ S. 30

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i. **Right to Legal Redress:** PWDs have the right to seek legal remedies for any damage they have suffered.¹⁰² To access these rights, PWDs are required to obtain a PCD from the NCPWD.¹⁰³ In certain cases, a temporary certificate may be issued by a doctor with the approval of the Commission if a disability is discovered during treatment.¹⁰⁴

6.0. CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH DISABILITY RIGHTS PROTECTION IN NIGERIA DESPITE THE ACT

This study observed that PWDs are still very much marginalised. Some are stigmatised and denied even the basic privileges provided under the Act. The evidence is obvious as they are found on every street of the country begging and soliciting alms to survive.

The study also observed that up till today, a very high percentage of public structures in private and public institutions like schools, banks, health care centres, etc., are not at par with the provisions of the Act, hence, not disability-friendly. Despite the provisions on the accessibility of public structures under the Act which was to be implemented five years after the passage of the Act, it is six years past and most of these institutions have not made their structures accessible to disabled persons.

The height of discrimination continues unabated even with the Act. In most communities, persons with disabilities are ostracised and often given all sorts of names. To compound the situation, they cannot even enforce their rights under the Act because of lack of accessibility due to their inability to approach the court. Most of them do not know what it takes to seek redress in the court and then the process and financial requirement coupled with court structures in the country makes it difficult for them to seek legal redress. All of these make the provisions of the Act just a mere expression that cannot be met.

The study also revealed that disabled persons are not thought of or even involved most times decisions about their welfare are taken. This explains why the Act takes much work to implement. Until today, public institutions have not been faithful to the 5% employment requirement for the disabled population. However, the Act still needs to provide for the body to enforce this or at least checkmate the institutions' activities to ensure they align with the inclusion mission.

The study also observed that the political ground in the country had not been infused with the provisions of the Act. No political party has presented a candidate even for the office of a councillor from the disabled population.

Challenges of Implementation of Disability Laws in Nigeria

The following challenges contribute to the inadequate implementation of laws protecting the rights of persons with disabilities in Nigeria:

1. Lack of Political Will

The political will that can influence the implementation of disability policies and programs in Nigeria is weak and lethargic. This has resulted in a lack of commitment to resources and support for policies and laws on the rights of PWDs. The Lagos State Special Peoples' Law 2011¹⁰⁵ for instance, is the first disability law in Nigeria, yet the implementation of the Law has been a challenge; even 14 years after its enactment, discrimination and stigmatisation PWDs is still prevalent in many parts of Lagos State, and this has limited their access to essential services and opportunities.¹⁰⁶ Besides, the Office for Disability Affairs has been poorly funded and has limited capacity to carry out its mandate effectively. The absence of strong institutional structures and mechanisms to support the implementation of the Law has also contributed to the slow progress.¹⁰⁷ The same is the case of NCPWD established under the Disability Act 2019.

2. Lack of Data

There is a lack of accurate and comprehensive data of PWDs in Nigeria. This makes it challenging to plan and implement effective disability policies and programs.

3. Lack of Coordination

There is a lack of coordination among government agencies, non-governmental organizations (N.G.O.s), and Disabled Persons' Organizations (D.P.O.s). This has resulted in a duplication of efforts and a need for coherent policies and programs.

¹⁰² S. 1(3)

¹⁰³ S. 22

¹⁰⁴ *Ibid*

¹⁰⁵ Ogunbiyi K., *Citizens with Disabilities and the Rest of Us*, (Feb 2023) available from <https://www.africmil.org/citizens-with-disabilities-and-the-rest-of-us/> accessed 2nd, March, 2025

¹⁰⁶ *Ibid*

¹⁰⁷ *Ibid*

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4. Inadequate Training

There is a lack of adequate training for government officials, service providers, and the general public on disability issues. This results in a lack of understanding and knowledge about disability rights and how to provide effective services and support to disabled persons.¹⁰⁸

5. Lack of Required Infrastructure

It is unfortunate to hear that most public buildings in Nigeria lack the required infrastructural outfit to enable accessibility for persons with disabilities, such as lifts, ramps, handrails, and proper parking spaces.¹⁰⁹ This constitutes a great challenge for people with disabilities to navigate public spaces and access essential services. Even with the mandate under the Act, most public buildings have not complied with the accessibility requirements for public buildings.

6. Limited Awareness and Sensitization

There is also a significant issue with limited awareness and sensitization about disability issues in Nigeria¹¹⁰. This lack of understanding often spur out stigmatisation and discrimination against persons with disabilities. Section 2 of the Disability Act, 2019 is intended to promote awareness and respect for the rights and contributions of persons with disabilities. The failure of the Federal Ministry of Information to fulfill its mandate, the insufficient allocation of resources by M.D.A.s responsible for disability affairs, and the lack of resources for operations of disability commissions in some states make that provision of the Law impotent and inactive.¹¹¹

7. Non-Domestication of the D.A.P.D.A., 2019

It is about four years after the promulgation of the D.A.P.D.A. 2019, only a few states have laws to protect the rights of people with disabilities. These states are spread across different regions of the country. In the North Central region, the states that have laws protecting PWDs are Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, and Plateau. In the North-East region, Bauchi State has disability-friendly policies. In the North-West region, the states with laws protecting the rights of PWDs are Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Sokoto, and Zamfara.¹¹² In the South-East region, Abia and Anambra states have implemented disability-friendly policies. In the South-South region, Cross River and Edo states have laws protecting people with disabilities. Ekiti, Lagos, Ondo, and Oyo states have disability-friendly policies in the South-West region.¹¹³

While it is commendable that some states in Nigeria have implemented laws to protect the rights of people with disabilities, all states must follow suit to create a more inclusive society for everyone. It should not only stop at domestication. Implementation is what is desirable.

8. Challenge of Access to Justice

It is concerning to hear that police stations, correctional centers, and courtrooms nationwide lack accessibility aids for persons with disabilities, despite the mandates in Sections 3 to 6 of the Act. Accessibility is a fundamental right for persons with disabilities, and the necessary measures must be implemented to ensure equal access to all physical structures.¹¹⁴ Furthermore, the lack of adequate measures to promote the legal rights of persons with disabilities as provided in the law in all aspects of society is a severe issue. The Commission and other Right enforcement bodies need more funding and capacity to achieve this. The road to seeking justice is still very rough, costly, and tortuous for disabled persons. For instance, Daniel Onwe, the president of the Association of Lawyers with Disabilities, puts the whole gist this way:

The justice administration system in Nigeria was not designed with persons with disabilities in mind. To date, sign language interpreters for the deaf and Braille material and other facilities for the visually impaired are still totally absent in our courts. Courtrooms and court environments generally have no facilities to cater to the peculiarities of persons with disabilities. The same applies to the practices and procedures of the court. This is most worrisome for junior lawyers with disabilities who do not have

¹⁰⁸ Atoyebi, O., Appraisal of Legal Framework for the Protection of the Rights of Disabled Persons in Nigeria. *The Nigerian Lawyer*, (April 21, 2023) available from <https://thenigerianlawyer.com/appraisal-of-legal-framework-for-the-protection-of-the-rights-of-disabled-persons-in-nigeria/> accessed 2nd March, 2025

¹⁰⁹ *Ibid*

¹¹⁰ *Ibid*

¹¹¹ *Ibid*

¹¹² C.C.D. Urges F.G., 17 States to Recognise Persons With Disabilities (2022). Available from <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.channelstv.com/2022/12/03/ccd-urges-fg-17-states-to-recognise-persons-with-disabilities/amp/> Accessed 3rd March, 2025

¹¹³ *Ibid*

¹¹⁴ Odeniyi S, People with Disabilities Road to Justice Remains Tortuous, Costly, Punch (Dec 2022) <https://punchng.com/for-pwds-in-nigeria-road-to-justice-remains-tortuous-costly-2/> accessed 5th March, 2025

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cars and who cannot employ aides to accompany them to courts. The situation is more frustrating to them. I used to be there, and I know how it feels. Handling cases for P.W.D.s are majorly *probono*, as most of them are not of means.¹¹⁵

With this situation, the provision for legal remedy in the D.A.P.D.A., 2019, will only be effective in the book, making a caricature of the rights of disabled people.

7.0. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Flowing from the preceding analysis, the study concluded that despite the enactment of the Disability Act of 2019, persons with disabilities are still not included in society. Their basic rights provided under the Act are not yet to be attained. The structures required to implement the Act are not yet in place, or where they are, they are either weak or unavailable. Only when these structures are set in place and passionately monitored will the desired result be achieved. Based on the research findings and the conclusions drawn above, the following are recommended:

a. The NCPWD as a body set up under the Act to monitor the implementation of the Act must wake up and receive life to ensure that all institutions required to implement the provisions of the Act do so and do it accordingly;

Full implementation of sanction regimes for corporate or personal bodies is required to set the standard for the maximal operation of the Act;

a. INEC should ensure that before allowing any political party to contest for election, it must show that it has at least 5% of its candidature from the PWDs's population. This should be considered as an amendment to the Act. It will only bring forth the desired result if more provisions exist for political participation;

b. Public buildings and infrastructures such as schools, hospitals, car parks, banks, and recreational centers should be designed with PWDs in mind. Institutions whether private or public should put slopes, lumps, and lifts in higher buildings in order for them to reach academic, social, health, and communal goals;

c. The governments at all levels should provide grants or set up funds to encourage creativity and innovation amongst PWDs;

d. For proper implementation of the right to seek redress in court, this study recommends that disabled persons' cases should be prioritized before the court. Better still, a section of the court should be created to handle cases of PWDs;

e. Policies and plans from government to institutional levels concerning people with disabilities must be put into action; and

f. Communities especially religious bodies should be aware of the importance of treating each member within and outside the community with much love, care, and support regardless of the condition one has. Communities should understand that people with disabilities are part and parcel of the community, and we should accord them all necessary support. Implementing the Act can start with the family, the community, the church, or the mosque. There should be a re-orientation for the benefits of understanding that disability does not mean liability.

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